

NEOLIVER

AUTOMATED GENERATION OF DENSE, FUNCTIONAL AND PERFUSABLE BIOPRINTED LIVER CONSTRUCTS FOR TRANSPLANTATION

Generate millions of multicellular spheroids from patient-derived organoids.

Bioprint spheroids using laser-induced forward transfer (LIFT) to create vascularized liver constructs.

Integrate functional blood vessels to engineer the first autologous liver ready for transplantation.

Validate safety and efficacy in immune-deficient pigs as a preclinical model.

Develop a clinical validation plan, scaling strategy and a health technology assessment for first-in-human trials.

Follow **NEOLIVER** to see how we are delivering a disruptive, life-saving alternative to donor organ shortages.

